
**ROLE OF TEACHER IN A UNIVERSITY FOR HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHING
LEARNING THROUGH ICT AND E- LEARNING**

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Abstract

In the level of higher education teacher role is very crucial for teaching learning process. Teachers are gaining different skill which is related with teaching learning ICT tools. Systematic management of ICT tools and E-learning materials always help for accessible all over the place with equal manner for every learners. Our great teachers always enhance his or her knowledge, skills, methods, style, etc. In this paper objectives are study the role of teacher's management ICT skills in a university and study the role of teacher's management E- learning process in a university in higher education. Methodology followed secondary data descriptive analysis. Researcher collected data from different sources there are websites, journal articles, e-books reports, virtual observation of various organization and commission, articles published in local papers, national and international etc. ICT and E-learning will be stand by harnessing learning innovatively. Access to e-books, digital learning resources, digital repository, etc. will be developed by the student support services. This will also be used for online capacity building for open and distance teacher training.

Keywords: Education, university, teaching, modern technology, ICT, E-learning.

Introduction

Information and communication technology (ICT) & electronic learning (E-learning) paly very crucial role in transforming world leaning environment. In the digital era maximum learners are flexible to use e learning method with the help of ICT tools. We are all known that teaching learning process can't complete without a skilled teachers. Now teachers are facing always challenging environment during class room as well as others academic activities. Our teachers all times are engaging others activities after taking his/ her classes. Most of all necessary work done by online mode through ICT. A fundamental concept and experience to successful healthy education means relationship between teacher and learner. When educational policy have to introduce on the field of ICT and E learning, told about need of teachers and students, it's also be accessible for teachers and students both according to work. Main feature of UNESCO's, using ICT in preparing programs for teaching training, where in-service or pre-service.

Here management is key term in this study because without proper management skills its cant work in a university. When a work done in a systemic manner and scientific way is called management. Teacher is playing big role of a very important for ICT tools in a university level. Teachers are acquire

knowledge and very much updated according to learner needs and modifying her or his teaching strategies for various purpose. “It is essential that potential users have a sound understanding of how to use new ICTs beneficially, and a cultural view of the relationship between learning and technology” (Leach, Ahmed, Makalima, & Power, 2005). The UNESCO (2008) ICT competency standards for teachers go further, describing three approaches: technological literacy, knowledge deepening, and knowledge creation. In the part of E- learning process lots of tools like Wikis, Digital textbooks, blogs; Social book marketing, storytelling Games, social networking, virtual world, E-portfolios there are most usable things.(Innes, &Wilton, 2018).

Need and Significance of the Study:

Needs of this study is relevant to our societies as well as our how university’s teaching-learning and educational others work through technological guidance’s. Our teacher is main pillar in a university, he or she can headily all the difficulties with his or her smiley face. How to students can gaining different kind of knowledge, experiences, better learning environment, practical knowledge, etc.? What are the basic requirement of a student for learning purpose? In a university will work in the different stages in a systematic manner and this type of work done by academician and administrators through the use of ICT tools.

E-learning content and materials is very crucial for teaching learning process in a university. Teacher are manage all the necessary step through ICT tools. In this study find the role of teachers transforming management skills on ICT and E-learning process in a university.

Objectives of the Study

- a. To study the role of teacher’s management ICT skills in a university.
- b. To study the role of teacher’s management E- learning process in a university.

Methodology of the Study

Secondary data based paper, Researcher collected data from different sources there are e-books reports, websites, virtual observation of various organization, journal articles, national and international articles published in local papers, etc. That paper will give a brief description of Role of Teacher transforming ICT and E-learning Management for higher education In a University.

According to our objectives here teacher, ICT, E- learning, skills, professional development etc. is most essential terms for brief description of this paper.

Role of teacher on Management step of a university through ICT and E learning

Teachers and students are asset in a university, learners can want to learn every day from teachers, due to teachers will be updated own self. Here a teacher can works in the different stages like...

Fig: 1. Main role of a teacher in a university.

E-learning

E-Learning is basically the **delivery of learning by internet**. **Online learning** can be thought of as subset of broader e-learning category because it refers specially to contain delivered by internet or intranet.

Under UNU software licence, education sectors can free access of learning resources. Now a days online E- materials Open source online learning system is growing fast in the education at business world.

Significance of e-learning

Its deals with **flexible learning** where is not possible to access offline mode of learning, there e-learning can handle the situation. It is means to effective and efficient learning to 2 its ease of access and pace being determined by learner.

It can be beneficial leverage to **disseminate information** about and catalyse adaptation, adoption, translation and distribution of rare educational resource distributed across various media and forms this will help promote its **wide spread availability** and extensive use.

It support distance **learning with Wide Area Network**. It addresses the practical side of learning by organising the topics to be taught and creating multimedia CD ROMs or websites. An important advantage is that hyper-linking is possible and having interactive parts illustrating difficult things are for doing exercises is also possible.

Meaning of ICT

A university teacher can shearing knowledge for student in the different ways and every teachers developed skill through govt. and non govt. organisation.

During training period teacher will be accessed ICT skills on the basis of his or her ability and quality. Government of India has been initiative how to enrich teacher ability on ICT and E learning field. “**Microsoft Shiksha**” training programme is focused on using ICTs application teaching learning for training teachers. This training programme developed to skills and apply in the real ground of teaching practices.

In India, several programme has been initiatives for fulfilled for objectives of learning. The **Sakshat Portal** for Government of India initiative like a National Program on Technology Education Learning (NPTEL), the Multimedia Educational Resource for Learning and Online Teaching (MERLOT) seek to create quality digital contain for different level of education.

Major modern Technologies for teacher

- Computers
- Software Applications,
- Electronics
- Communication Network

In the management point of view, teachers are work through...

- ERP –Enterprise Resource Planning (SAP for Budgeting)
- CRM –Student Relationship Management
- EMS –Employee Management System
- PMS –Performance Management System

Technology used in Education for teaching learning process

In the higher education this all the diameter are very important tools of a teachers and students for teaching learning process. In a university organise flexible method for adopting new generation learners enhance knowledge for better education.

Role of teacher in higher education through ICT and E- learning implementation

- ✓ To implement main **principle** of lifelong and all round development learning education.
- ✓ To increase flexibility of educational **services and medium of instruction** methods.
- ✓ To promote **equal opportunity** for all learners to obtain education and information in the proper way.
- ✓ To access a system of **expanding and collecting** various type educational information from global.
- ✓ More focused on **distance education** through **MOOCs and SWAYAM**.
- ✓ **E- Literacy of all citizen** especially focused for students.
- ✓ To developed the **culture of learning** at all level of institutions (development of learning skills, expansion of optimal education, open source of education, etc.)

On the other hand more role of teacher in a university of higher education on different dimension...

Teacher role and management for Improvement ICT and E- learning

- Improving the quality of teaching learning is critical issues of whole world. The teacher and institution can create healthy environment for learning. E- Learning and ICT can helps several ways concern the quality of education.

- Increasing learner’s activities engagement and learning motivation by proper management of teaching methods.
- Providing by various type of facilitating for the enhancing physical skills.
- University also provided skill oriented teacher training programme. Here E- Learning and ICTs are also transformational tools which can for creating a learner centred environment.
- Different kind of ICTs and E-Learning materials such as videos, text sound and colourful moving images, multimedia computers software, audio books, television that can be used to provide engage the student in learning process.
- The teachers strongly felt that the **visual audio combination of integrated** judiciously with the textbook and syllabus can work wonders in getting across abstract concepts and logic to the children in short span of time.

Helping hand for management ICT and E- Learning skills for teacher’s

Digital Resources for teachers in a university

- ✓ Desktop and laptops
- ✓ Projector
- ✓ Digital cameras
- ✓ Printer
- ✓ Photocopier
- ✓ Tablets
- ✓ Popplet
- ✓ Pen Drive
- ✓ Microphones
- ✓ DVDs and CDs
- ✓ Word processing
- ✓ Spreadsheets
- ✓ Animation
- ✓ Presentation software

Source- Internet

- ✓ World Wide Web
- ✓ Android App
- ✓ IPod
- ✓ Web boards
- ✓ Scanners
- ✓ Video Games

Cloud Service

Application Services (services on demand)
Gmail, Google Calendar

Payroll, HR, CRM etc.

Sugarm CRM, IBM Lotus Live

Platform Services (resources on demand)

Middleware, Interrogation, Messaging, Information, connectivity, etc.

AWS, IBM Virtual images, Boomi, Cast-iron, Google Appengine

Infrastructure as services (physical assets as services)

IBM Blue house, VMWare, Amazon EC2, Microsoft Azure Platform, Sun Para scale and more.

Conclusion

Last part of this paper we are conclude that teacher has a potential to improve quality education through ICT and E-learning. Interaction between students and teachers more flexible, attractive, collaborative as well as systematic manner during classroom and distance learning. Smart university framework will host classroom online using the help of various learning management system and there is no need of owing a classroom at all. The smart management also introduce various software which can be helped in the management and learning of students. CT provided different kind of tools, this tools is very handy and more usability in learning purpose. Teachers create accessible opportunities for bringing education to doorstep of learners living rural areas. In a university also play vital role regarding high speed internet delivery of uniform quality contained at reduced cost bringing the cost of education from very high to very low and can serve multiple teaching functions and diverse audiences. It facilitates in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of education Administration and by policy by improving the quality of administrative activities and processes.

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